

A STUDY OF COMPLEXES OF BLUE PEROXYCHROMIC ACID WITH PYRIDINE AND PIPERIDINE

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Different samples of pyridine and piperidine complexes with ethereal blue peroxychromic acid have been prepared and analysed, and their empirical and molecular formulae suggested.

Riesefeld (*Ber. Naturforsch. Ges. Freiburg*, 1906, 17, 1062) established four oxidation products representing blue peroxychromic acid: (1) mono-perchromates, HCrO_5 , with an organic nitrogen base (blue or violet); (2) di-perchromates, RH_2CrO_7 or $\text{RCrO}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ (blue); (3) tri-perchromates, R_3CrO_9 (red); (4) complex chromium tetroxides, $\text{CrO}_4 \cdot 3\text{NH}_3$.

Wiede (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2178) prepared the compounds of the type (1) and assigned the formula $\text{RCrO}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$.

Rosenheim, Hakki and Krause (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.* 1932, 209, 175) discussed the structure of perchromates and suggested the following structure :

Schwarz and Giese (*Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 310; cf. *Ber.*, 1932, 65B, 871) suggested three formulae of blue potassium perchromates: KH_2CrO_7 , $\text{KCrO}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ and $\text{KCrO}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$.

The preparation and analysis of blue, slightly soluble, explosive TiCrO_5 indicated that the third formula was correct. They proposed the structural formula as double molecules $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ containing sexivalent chromium and numerous peroxide linkages.

A further study was made by Schwarz and Elstner (*Ber.*, 1936, 69B, 575) of the blue compound, believed by Riesefeld and Man (*Chem. Abs.*, 1914, 8, 1714) to be $\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The formula CrO_5 was confirmed by working with the pyridine complex of the blue peroxychromic acid, and the formula for the pyridine complex was assigned to be RCrO_5 (where R stands for one pyridine molecule). If the formula of the pyridine complex were accepted as RCrO_5 , the percentages of pyridine in the complex ought to have been 37.44, of chromium 24.64, and that of oxygen, 37.92. But when the percentages of pyridine, chromium and oxygen were determined from the pyridine complex in this laboratory, it came out to be between 47 and 47.3 (for pyridine), 30.04 and 30.31 (for chromium) and 22.45 and 22.91 (for oxygen). Moreover, various formulae suggested by various workers clearly indicate chromium to be always present in the acidic part of the complex. It has been observed by Rai and Prakash (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1954, 275, 95) that the decomposition product of the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid contains chromium in basic as well as in acidic parts. Therefore the present paper records the study of the pyridine and piperidine complexes of the ethereal blue peroxychromic acid.

The complexes of pyridine and piperidine were prepared as laid down under "Experimental". The complexes were found to be insoluble in almost all organic

solvents but soluble in caustic soda solution. When the solutions of pyridine and piperidine complexes in NaOH solution were kept for a day or so, green precipitates of chromium hydroxide were obtained. When the precipitates were filtered and the filtrates were acidified with acetic acid, and to these barium chloride and lead acetate solutions were added separately, yellow precipitates of barium chromate and lead chromate were formed. Further, the acidified solutions of the filtrates also liberated iodine from KI solution. These qualitative tests prove that chromium is present in the basic as well as in acidic parts of the complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation and Examination of Pyridine and Piperidine Complexes.—Blue peroxychromic acid was prepared by taking 5% chromic acid solution (800 c.c.) to which 450 c.c. of ether was added. The mixture was cooled in ice and to it 320 c.c. of 20 vol. H_2O_2 , also cooled in ice, added. The blue peroxychromic acid was formed which on shaking dissolved in ether. The aqueous layer was separated in a separating funnel. The ethereal layer of blue peroxychromic acid was taken at the temperature of ice in a flask and made up to 500 c.c. with ether, and kept in ice.

The ethereal blue peroxychromic acid (50 c.c.) was taken in a number of Erlenmeyer flasks and varying volumes of pyridine and piperidine were added separately. After keeping these overnight the complexes were found to be precipitated from ethereal solutions.

The above precipitates were filtered separately and washed with 5% alcoholic solution till no yellow coloration was obtained, and then finally washed with ether and dried in a desiccator. Different samples were analysed separately.

Sample No. (50 c.c. each)	...	A	B	C	D
Pyridine (added in c.c.)	...	25	50	75	100
Piperidine (added in c.c.)	...	25	50	75	100

Estimation of Total Chromium.—Definite masses of the pyridine and piperidine complexes were taken separately in weighed silica crucibles and heated at first slowly and then strongly. The complexes on heating decomposed to Cr_2O_3 . These were weighed which gave the weight of Cr_2O_3 . Care was taken in heating the complexes as these were highly explosive.

Determination of the Oxidation Values of the Pyridine and Piperidine Complexes in NaOH solution in terms of volumes of N/20 Sodium Thiosulphate soln. by Iodimetry.—Definite masses of pyridine and piperidine complexes were dissolved separately in 5 c.c. of N-NaOH solution and each solution was made up to 100 c.c.

The solutions (25 c.c. each) were taken and added to aqueous solutions of KI and were acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil.) till distinctly acidic. Iodine was liberated which was titrated with the standard hypo solution using starch as indicator.

Estimation of Chromium in the Basic part as well as Oxidation Values of Filtrates in terms of volume of N/20 Sodium Thiosulphate solution.—From the above 100 c.c. solutions, 25 c.c. aliquots were separately taken in beakers and kept in a bath of

boiling water till green chromium hydroxide was completely precipitated. These were filtered over gravimetric filter papers and washed with hot water till the precipitates were free from NaOH and chromate ions. The precipitates were then ignited in weighed silica crucibles and weighed as Cr_2O_3 . This gave the amounts of chromium oxide corresponding to the amounts of chromium in the basic parts of the two complexes.

The filtrates were taken along with wash water and made distinctly acidic with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and titrated iodimetrically with $N/20$ sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator.

Estimation of Nitrogen or Pyridine and Piperidine.—This was carried out by Dumas' method. The percentage of nitrogen as well as of pyridine and piperidine are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Sample No.	% Nitrogen.	% Pyridine or piperidine.	% Total Cr.	% Cr in the basic part.	$N/20$ Hypo reqd.	$N/20$ Hypo used for the filtrate.
A. Pyridine complex.						
A	8.36	47.17	30.20	15.20	21.70 c.c.	21.40 c.c.
B	8.40	47.30	30.25	15.07	21.50	21.60
C	8.34	47.05	30.04	15.15	21.60	21.40
D	8.35	47.00	30.31	15.17	21.50	21.60
B. Piperidine complex.						
A	9.88	59.90	22.00	11.20	14.50	14.60
B	9.84	59.80	22.50	11.30	14.40	14.50
C	9.88	59.90	22.60	11.25	14.60	14.40
D	9.88	59.90	22.60	11.30	14.50	14.40

From the above table the empirical formula for the pyridine complex is found to be $\text{RCrO}_{2.5}$ or $\text{R}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_5$ and for the piperidine complex; $\text{R}_{1.6}\text{CrO}_{2.5}$ or $\text{R}_5\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_5$ (where R stands for one molecule of organic bases).

CONCLUSION

It is quite clear from the above table that the chromium is present in the acidic as well as in basic part of the complexes in equal proportions. Therefore considering the above data and the chemical properties of the complexes, the molecular formula for the pyridine complex may be written as (a) $\text{R}_2\text{Cr}(\text{CrO}_5)$, (b) $\text{R}_4\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})$ or (c) $\text{R}_4\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_5)_2$; and for the piperidine complex as (a) $\text{R}_2\text{Cr}(\text{CrO}_5)$, (b) $\text{R}_6\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})$ and (c) $\text{R}_6\text{Cr}_2(\text{CrO}_5)_2$. It is important to note that the number of molecules of piperidine is greater than those of pyridine in the corresponding complexes in contrast to the observations of the previous workers (Wiede, *loc. cit.*) who mentioned similar complexes with pyridine and piperidine.

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